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EMD – Eye Movement Desensitization

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Abstract

To investigate the (putative) affect-reducing effect of the clinical method lateral eye movement (EMD) in the normal range an experiment was conducted, assuming that *arousal reduction* and *mood elevation* compared to other types of distractions are significant. Possible placebo and experimenter effects are discussed. An emotionally colored arousal was generated, followed by lateral eye movement and two variants of distraction. Before and after the treatment, arousal and subjectively experienced mood of subjects was measured. The implementation was camouflaged to rule out any placebo effects. Results suggest an effect in arousal reduction compared to distraction in general and to a specific distraction condition in particular. There were no effects on the subjectively perceived mood. To which extent the method could be confirmed was discussed.

Introduction

The method of *Eye Movement Desensitization* (EMD, EMDR, res.) was developed by Francine Shapiro in 1989 to treat Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD¹). According to DSM (APA, 2013) PTSD is defined by (a) constant reliving of a traumatic experience, (b) avoidance of thoughts about that situation and (c) an associated increased level of *arousal*.

Shapiro (1989) describes the process of treating PTSD with EMDR as follows: At the beginning, the client should visualize the traumatic event as vividly and in as much detail as possible. The therapist now moves his finger rhythmically from right to left at a distance of $d = 30$ cm from the client's head and with a deflection of $d = 30$ cm, with a pendulum movement per second. During the imagining of the traumatic event, the patient generally follows the therapist's finger with his eyes until the

¹ See Guideline Development Panel for the Treatment of PTSD in Adults & American Psychological Association (2019).

imaginings become *bearable*. The length of such a set is given as $k = 15$ to 25 lateral eye movements. A stable effect was reported in a follow-up study after three months for $n = 22$ persons.

As possible neurophysiological explanation, Shapiro (1989) refers to the fact that experiencing a traumatic event disturbs the balance between *excitation* and *inhibition* in the brain (Pavlov, 1927). According to Shapiro, lateral eye movements should be able to *restore* this balance. However, a full explanation of the underlying physiological mechanisms is yet to come, for further approaches see e.g. Stickgold (2002), Söndergaard & Elofsson (2008) or Pierce et al. (2021).

The advantage of the method is clearly due to the fact that treatments are rather short and so clients are not exposed to intense fear for a longer period of time (Shapiro, 1996). Follow-ups by different authors, who mainly describe individual clinical cases, led to different results. A successful treatment of a rape victim with EMDR is reported (Wolpe & Abrams, 1991). A larger study, in which $n = 73$ cases out of $N = 78$ were classified as slightly improved to cured, reports a large number of partial relapses (Marquis, 1991). This contrasts with the perfect stability reported by Shapiro.

Oswalt et. al (1993) assumed that Shapiro's positive results could be caused by a placebo effect or the author's (Shapiro's) positive expectations, and therefore used independent observers in their study, reporting the successful treatment of three of the eight cases. Vaughan et al. first examined the effect of EMDR on the major symptom groups of PTSD in 1994 and found that all three categories of PTSD (see above) as well as depression were significantly improved immediately after treatment with EMDR. At a follow-up, however, only the categories *re-experiencing* and *avoidance* were significant, arousal and depression had increased again. Additional life stress is suspected as an explanation. The authors of the studies mentioned above suggest that, in order to further examine the *mechanisms* of EMDR, the question should primarily be answered as to whether *fixing* a stable target or any other form of *distraction* would have the same effect.

The aim of the present study was to address these questions by experimentally inducing an emotionally colored arousal, one of the three symptom groups of PTSD and investigate whether lateral eye movements reduce this activation more than (a) fixing an inert target or (b) a different kind of distraction. Arousal was accomplished by placing subjects in a situation that elicited evaluation anxiety, as the latter was found to be significantly positively correlated with arousal levels. Furthermore, the results of an experiment on *social facilitation* and *social monitoring* also point to such a relation (Guerin, 1983).

In order to exclude possible placebo effects, arousal was measured indirectly via *short-term memory* performance, since material learned under an increased activation level can be reproduced more poorly in direct replication than material learned under low arousal (Walker, 1958; Kesner, 1973). However, this negative association between arousal and memory is not substantial. For this reason, the mood of subjects additionally was measured via parts of the *Eigenschaftswörterliste* EWL questionnaire (Janke & Debus, 1978). The intended opacity of the experiment should have been only slightly affected by this.

Given that lateral eye movement *decreases* arousal levels (Shapiro, 1989), evaluation anxiety *increases* arousal levels (Zajonc, 1965; Guerin, 1983) and there is a negative association between arousal and short-term memory performance (Walker, 1958; Kesner, 1973), it follows, that in aroused individuals lateral eye movement leads (1) to *improved* short-term memory performance and (2) to a more *positive* assessment of current mood, compared to a condition of sole distraction.

Method

Sample

The sample consisted of $n = 51$ psychology students at the Karl-Franzens University. Participation was voluntary and part of the education.

Materials and apparatus

A desktop computer was placed to the right of the subject, and a video-camera on a tripod to the left (fig. 1). Subjects were filmed throughout the experiment to *maintain* a constant anxiety-provoking situation. The recordings were not included in the evaluation and have been deleted. The experimenter sat between the video camera and the subjects.

Fig. 1: Arrangement.

EMD (lateral eye movement):

In order to make the eye movements imperceptible to the subject, a *moving bar* was rendered on the monitor (see fig. 2). The bar changed color from green to blue with $p_1 = 0.125$ per pass. Each blue bar was to be reported as *blue* in order to disguise the real purpose and to keep the subjects' attention through an apparent reaction task. One run (from left to right and back) lasted for $t_1 = 3$ seconds, this $n_1 = 60$ times resulted in $t_1 = 3$ minutes.

Fig. 2: EMD procedure (60 passes a 3 sec., $p_{(blue)} = 0.125$, equals $n = 7.5$ expected events e_1).

ABL_a (active distraction)

In order to fix a central object, four rectangles were rendered on the monitor, see fig. 3. These appeared either blue or green every $t_2 = 3$ seconds ($p = 0.5$). Once all four rectangles displayed the same color ($p_2 = 0.125$), subject had to report (*blue* or *green*). The length of the procedure was again $t_2 = 3$ minutes. The program for timing and rendering procedures was realized in QBasic under MS-DOS operating system.

Fig. 3: ABL_a procedure ($n = 60$ passes a $t = 3$ sec., $p_{(same\ color)} = 0.5^4 \times 2 = 0.125$, equals $n = 7.5$ expected events e_2).

ABL_p (passive distraction)

In order to distract subjects without active participation, a $t_3 = 3$ minute piece of music (*Atmospheric moods, the power of relaxation*) was presented.

Questionnaires

The *objects* subtest of the *Lern- und Gedächtnistest* LGT-3 (Bäumler, 1973) was used to indicate short-term memory performance. EWL was additionally used to ascertain subjective mood. The $m = 60$ items were divided into two parallel forms², each with $m = 30$ items. For the variable *subjective mood*, ratings of items 1, 5, 10, 16, 19, 22, 6, 12, 17, 23, 27 and 29 were summed up. A high score indicates a negative mood.

Experimental plan

At t_0 all $k = 3$ groups experienced arousal induction. At t_1 and t_2 subjective mood (EWL) and short-term memory (LGT) were assessed. In between, the group-specific treatment (*EMD*, ABL_a and ABL_p) took place (see table 1). In order to rule out time effects, the groups were allocated alternately. For this purpose, the parallel forms of LGT-3 and EWL were completely balanced.

Table 1: Experimental design, 1×3 design with repeated measurement.

	t_0	t_1	Treatment	t_2
<i>experimental</i>		LGT ₁ ,EWL ₁	<i>EMD</i>	LGT ₂ , EWL ₂
<i>control group 1</i>	Arousal	LGT ₁ ,EWL ₁	ABL_a	LGT ₂ , EWL ₂
<i>control group 2</i>		LGT ₁ ,EWL ₁	ABL_p	LGT ₂ , EWL ₂

Procedure

Subjects were recruited for a *seemingly* cognitive performance experiment. After entering the room, it was explained that performance aspects would be measured and related to personality traits. Subjects were asked if they consented to being filmed throughout the experiment, after consent was given, the experimenter turned on the camera and left the room under a pretext.

After $t = 3$ minutes he returned, each subject received a parallel form of the EWL and was instructed to fill out the EWL based on its current condition. After that, subjects had $t = 30$ seconds to memorize $k = 20$ LGT-3 *objects* and were told that they would immediately have to verbally reproduce as many objects as possible.

After learning and testing phases, subjects were asked to sit in front of the monitor, received a brief demonstration of the task (*EMD*, ABL_a) and performed it. In order to avoid any conjecture about the true purpose of the procedure, *EMD* condition did not *explicitly* state to follow the bar with the

² Items for the respective factors were randomly assigned. So these are not *real* parallel forms.

eyes. Indeed, it occurred that almost all subjects actually performed lateral eye movements on their own. Music was played to control group 2 (ABL_p).

Then (see t_1) EWL and LGT-3 parallel forms were specified (instructions as above) and finally, all subjects were briefly informed about the true purpose of the experiment and dismissed.

Results

LGT-3

The mean number of reproduced images are shown in table 2. Evaluation was carried out by means of ONEWAY with repeated measurements. The interaction effect *treatment* \times *performance change* was significant ($F = 3.44, p > 0.04$). Cells marked with arrows in table 2 showed significant differences after *post hoc* comparison by means of LSD ($ABL_{at1} \leftrightarrow ABL_{at2}, p < 0.05$; $EMD_{t2} \leftrightarrow ABL_{at2}, p > 0.02$).

Table 2: Arithmetic mean and standard deviation of retained images in LGT-3 ($n = 17$ per cell).

Parameter/ Treatment	Performance change	
	LGT t_1	LGT t_2
<i>Mean</i>		
EMD	9.23	9.94
ABL_a	10.11	8.82
ABL_p	9.64	9.11
<i>Std. dev.</i>		
EMD	2.17	2.19
ABL_a	1.96	1.84
ABL_p	1.62	1.86

Furthermore, contrast revealed a significant interaction of EMD combined with both CGs \times change in performance ($F = 5.76, p > 0.02$) and of EMD combined with $ABL_a \times$ change in performance ($F = 6.62, p > 0.01$). The interaction of EMD combined with $ABL_p \times$ change in performance was on tendency level ($F = 2.53, p < 0.12$). Both CGs combined \times performance change showed no significant interaction (see fig. 3).

EWL

Since there was a tendency correlation between *subjective mood* and *experimenter* ($r_{t1} = 0.27, r_{t2} = 0.25$) the experimenter effect was eliminated using covariance analysis (ANCOVA). No main or interaction effects were significant (see table 3).

Scores, formed according to the EWL factors *introversion, disactivity, well-being, performance-related activity, anxiety-depression* and *emotional irritability* did not result in any significance.

In a factor analysis of the $m = 30$ items, $k = 7$ factors could be extracted at t_1 and $k = 9$ factors at t_2 according to the eigenvalue criterion and orthogonal rotation according to VARIMAX. Factor *subjective mood* ($\lambda_{1(t1)} = 4.87, \lambda_{1(t2)} = 7.62$) showed no significant effects in variance analysis of factor values.

Table 3: Arithmetic mean, standard dev. of the EWL score *subjective mood* ($n = 17$ per cell).

Parameter / Treatment	Mood change	
	EWL t_1	EWL t_2
<i>Mean</i>		
EMD	35.47	36.23
ABL _a	36.82	36.11
ABL _p	35.52	36.82
<i>Std. dev.</i>		
EMD	5.34	7.25
ABL _a	5.80	6.93
ABL _p	6.32	7.83

Concluding, *EMD* did not improve *short-term memory* performance or lead to a better subjective assessment of current *mood* in general. However, there was an interaction between *performance change* and *treatment*: *ABL_a* control group showed (a) significant *deterioration* in memory performance and (b) at t_2 significantly worse memory performance *compared* to *EMD* test group (see [table 2](#)).

Discussion

Our results from 1994 then already supported the concept of Shapiro from 1989 in that *short-term memory* was improved after *EMD* conditions compared to *distraction groups*, suggesting a treatment effect on *arousal* between groups. An EMDR-related improvement in *subjective mood* could not be confirmed. The differences in memory performance between *EMD* and *distraction in general* and for *active distraction* in particular are significant. For implications concerning working memory, EMDR and PTSD see e.g. de Jongh et al. (2013) or Wadji et al. (2022).

However, it would be conceivable that these effects are caused by an *arousal-increasing* effect of the distraction variants: *ABL_a* subjects were apparently confused and agitated by the *ambiguity* of the situation, even appeared to be more concerned with the task itself compared to subjects of the experimental condition *EMD*. For *ABL_p* condition it was observed that subjects became rather *nervous* and *restless* instead of relaxed. As for *ABL_a* this could be attributed (1) to a higher *difficulty level* of items (two colors to report, higher *information content* of the fixation object etc.). It would be conceivable that a same sequence of events e generated for each person should be preferred (2) to a *random* sequence, to be named (*blue bar* or *rectangles of the same color*) as the frequency of occurrence was spread rather widely around the expected number ($n \sim 8$) of events e (in some cases events where extremely seldom, which *increased* arousal of subjects, possibly caused by *non-reinforcement*). Further clarity could be gained by *physiological* measurements of arousal level (e.g. EDA, EEG, fMRI), whereby several measurement times could be introduced in order to register trend effects, see e.g. Richardson et al. (2009), Pagani et al. (2012) or di Lorenzo et al. (2015).

Given that no effects occurred in the subjectively experienced *mood*, would indicate that treatment conditions only touched on a *neutral*, non-affected arousal dimension, as a consistent dimensionality of the EWL was confirmed by the results of factor analysis. This could be an indication that arousal-inducing boundary conditions (*video-camera*, *waiting*, *fear of evaluation*) were not *efficient* enough implemented to be reflected in measurable negative emotions. *Explicit* evaluation or *several* observers present could do satisfaction to this requirement.

Still it may be unclear to what extent the *assumptions* of *psychology students* (serving as subjects) about the purpose of the study could falsify the results. A more *representative* sample being completely

unfamiliar with the subject area would be more appropriate here. Possible placebo effects could be examined more precisely by involving a *further* control group, to which the purpose of the study was *explained*.

Yet, results strongly suggested that lateral eye movement, even in the normal range, has hypotheses-conforming *effects on the arousal level*, which cannot be exclusively attributed to distraction effects. In further investigations, a more stable and more valid experimental modeling of all symptom groups of PTSD, constant test and control conditions and a multidimensional indication should therefore be aimed at. Meanwhile, the value of the method (EMD, EMDR, res.) has received broad confirmation and acceptance. EMDR was proved to be most effective in the treatment of PTSD as well as many other syndroms compared to several forms of different therapy, see also e.g. Shapiro & Maxfield (2002), Greenwald & Shapiro (2010), Oren & Solomon (2012), Brown et al. (2016), or Laliotis & Shapiro (2022). For an overview and outlook regarding the method itself, see Luber & Shapiro (2009), Valiente-Gómez et al. (2017) or de Jongh et al. (2019)³.

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References

- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5*. (5th ed.). APA, Washington, DC. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>
- Bäumler, G. (1974). *Lern- und Gedächtnistest: LGT-3*. Verlag für Psychologie, Göttingen: Hogrefe. <https://www.hogrefe.com/de/shop/lern-und-gedaechtnistest.html>
- Brown, S., Stowasser, J., & Shapiro, F. (2016). EMDR Therapy and the Treatment of Substance Abuse and Addiction. In: *Innovations in the Treatment of Substance Addiction*. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-43172-7_5
- De Jongh, A., Ernst, R., Marques, L., & Hornsveld, H. (2013). The impact of eye movements and tones on disturbing memories involving PTSD and other mental disorders. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, 44(4), 477—483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbtep.2013.07.002>
- De Jongh, A., Amann, B. L., Hofmann, A., Farrell, D., & Lee, C. W. (2019). The Status of EMDR Therapy in the Treatment of Posttraumatic Stress Disorder 30 Years After Its Introduction. *Journal of EMDR Practice and Research*, 13, 261—269. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1933-3196.13.4.261>
- Di Lorenzo, G. L. Monaco, L., Daverio, A., Santarnecchi, E., Verrdo, A. R., Niolu, C., Fernandez, I., Pagani, M., & Siracusano, A. (2015). EMDR Therapy Changes the Resting-state EEG. *European Psychiatry, Volume 30, Supplement 1*, 28—31, Page 677. ISSN 0924-9338. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-9338\(15\)30537-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-9338(15)30537-X).
- Guerin, B. (1983). Social facilitation and social monitoring: A test of three models. *British Journal of social Psychology*, 22(3), 203—214. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8309.1983.tb00585.x>
- Greenwald, R. & Shapiro, F. (2010). What Is EMDR?: Commentary by Greenwald and Invited Response by Shapiro. *Journal of EMDR Practice and Research*, 4, 170—179. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1933-3196.4.4.170>
- Guideline Development Panel for the Treatment of PTSD in Adults, & American Psychological Association. (2019). Summary of the clinical practice guideline for the treatment of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in adults. *American Psychologist*, 74(5), 59—607. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000473>
- Janke, W., & Debus, G. (1978). *Die Eigenschaftswörterliste EWL: EWL. Eine Mehrdimensionale Methode zur Beschreibung von Aspekten des Befindens*. Verlag für Psychologie, Göttingen: Hogrefe. <https://psy-lab.librarika.com/search/detail/170176>

³ The year of Francine Shapiro's tragic death.

- Kesner, R. (1973). A neuronal system analysis of memory storage and retrieval. *Psychological Bull*, 80(3), 177—203. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/h0034843>
- Lalotitis, D., & Shapiro, F. (2022). EMDR Therapy for Trauma-Related Disorders. In: *Evidence Based Treatments for Trauma-Related Psychological Disorders: A Practical Guide for Clinicians*. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-97802-0_11
- Luber, M., & Shapiro, F. (2009). Interview With Francine Shapiro: Historical Overview, Present Issues, and Future Directions of EMDR. *Journal of EMDR Practice and Research*, 3(4), 217—231. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1933-3196.3.4.217>
- Marquis, J. N. (1991). A report on seventy-eight cases treated by eye movement desensitization. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, 22(3), 187—192. [https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1016/0005-7916\(91\)90015-W](https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1016/0005-7916(91)90015-W)
- Oswalt, R., Anderson, M., Hagstrom, K., & Berkowitz, B. (1993). Evaluation of the one-session Eye-movement Desensitization Reprocessing procedure for eliminating traumatic memories. *Psychological Reports*, 73(1), 99—104. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.1993.73.1.99>
- Oren, E., & Solomon, R. M. (2012). EMDR therapy: An overview of its development and mechanisms of action. *Revue Européenne de Psychologie Appliquée/European Review of Applied Psychology*, 62, 197—203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erap.2012.08.005>
- Pagani, M., Di Lorenzo, G., Verardo, A. R., Nicolais, G., Monaco, L., Lauretti, G., & et al. (2012). Neurobiological Correlates of EMDR Monitoring – An EEG Study. *PLoS ONE* 7(9): e45753. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0045753>
- Pavlov, I. P. (1927). *Conditioned Reflexes: An Investigation of the Physiological Activity of the Cerebral Cortex*. Oxford University Press, London. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1927-02531-000>
- Pierce, Z. P., & Black, J. M. (2021). The Neurophysiology Behind Trauma-Focused Therapy Modalities Used to Treat Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Across the Life Course: A Systematic Review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*. SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380211048446>
- Richardson, P., Williams, S. R., Hепенstall, S., Gregory, L., McKie, S., & Corrigan, F. (2009). A Single-Case fMRI Study EMDR Treatment of a Patient With Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. *Journal of EMDR Practice and Research*, 3(1), 10—33. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1933-3196.3.1.10>
- Schrausser, D. G., Draxler, J., & Plechinger J. (1994). EMD - Eye Movement Desensitization. *Manuskript*. Institut für Psychologie, Karl Franzens Universität, Graz, Austria. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28498.02247/2>
- Shapiro, F. (1989). Eye movement desensitization: a new treatment for post-traumatic stress disorder. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, 20(3), 211—217. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7916\(89\)90025-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7916(89)90025-6)
- Shapiro, F. (1996). Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR): Evaluation of controlled PTSD research. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, 27(3), 209—218. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-7916\(96\)00029-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-7916(96)00029-8)
- Shapiro, F., & Maxfield, L. (2002). Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR): information processing in the treatment of trauma. *J Clin Psychol*, 58(8), 933—46. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.10068>
- Söndergaard, H. P., & Elofsson, U. (2008). Psychophysiological Studies of EMDR. *Journal of EMDR Practice and Research*, 2, 282—288. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1933-3196.2.4.282>
- Stickgold, R. (2002), EMDR: A putative neurobiological mechanism of action. *J. Clin. Psychol.*, 58, 61—75. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.1129>
- Valiente-Gómez, A., Moreno-Alcázar, A., Treen, D., Cedrón, C., Colom, F., Pérez, V., & Amann, B. L. (2017). EMDR beyond PTSD: A Systematic Literature Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8: 1668. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01668>
- Vaughan, K., Wiese, M., Gold, R., & Tarrier, N. (1994). Eye-movement desensitisation: Symptom change in post-traumatic stress disorder. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 164, 533—541. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1192/bjp.164.4.533>
- Wadji, D. L., Martin-Soelch, C., & Camos, V. (2022). Can working memory account for EMDR efficacy in PTSD? *BMC Psychology*, 10, 245ff. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-022-00951-0>
- Walker, E. L. (1958). Aktion decrement and ist relation to learning. *Psychological Review*, 65(3),129—142. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/h0049177>

- Wolpe, J., & Abrams, J. (1991). Post-traumatic stress disorder overcome by eye-movement desensitization: A case report. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, 22(1), 39—43.
[https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1016/0005-7916\(91\)90032-Z](https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1016/0005-7916(91)90032-Z)
- Zajonc, R. B. (1965). Social facilitation. *Science*, 149(Whole No. 3681), 269—274.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1126/science.149.3681.269>